

FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF A COST-EFFECTIVE POLY-HERBAL MOUTHWASH FOR MAINTAINING ORAL HYGIENE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Herbal mouthwashes have emerged as strong alternatives to chemical-based formulations. Combining two or more herbal ingredients into a polyherbal preparation is now considered an effective strategy to enhance the value of simple herbal products. In the present study, a polyherbal mouthwash was developed using different parts of *Mentha piperita* (peppermint), the wood and leaves of *Cinnamomum camphora* (camphor), and the leaves, flowers, and stems of *Thymus vulgaris* (thyme). Each plant material was collected, extracted separately, and subjected to phytochemical screening and quantitative analysis. The formulation was designed by optimizing various concentrations of the active constituents. Organoleptic evaluations were carried out, including the dissolution of preservatives, pH adjusters, and colorants, followed by incorporation of the herbal extracts and flavoring agents. Physicochemical tests such as pH determination, viscosity measurement, color and odor assessment, foaming capacity, stability testing, and specific gravity evaluation were performed to ensure the mouthwash's stability and effectiveness. When compared with a commercially available mouthwash, the prepared formulation exhibited a larger zone of inhibition, likely due to the synergistic action of the multiple herbs used. The results clearly indicate that polyherbal mouthwashes can significantly enhance the therapeutic performance of herbal formulations. The combination of *Mentha piperita*, *Cinnamomum camphora*, and *Thymus vulgaris* demonstrated promising outcomes for plaque reduction, gum health improvement, and prevention of oral diseases. In conclusion, natural ingredients show considerable potential in reducing oral discomfort, inhibiting microbial growth, and improving overall oral hygiene. However, further refinement, clinical validation, and comparative

studies are required to optimize the formulation's safety, efficacy, and user acceptability. Polyherbal oral care products ultimately hold strong promise as effective and accessible options for maintaining oral health and hygiene.

INTRODUCTION

Mouthwashes, also known as oral rinses or mouth rinses, are liquid solutions used for oral hygiene purposes and are commonly used as an adjunct to regular oral hygiene practices such as brushing and flossing, to help maintain oral health and hygiene (Radzki, Wilhelm-Węglarz, Pruska, Kusiak, & Ordyniec-Kwaśnica, 2022). They typically contain various active ingredients, including antimicrobial agents, fluoride, astringents, and flavoring agents, among others. These ingredients work together to reduce oral bacteria, plaque buildup, and bad breath, as well as to promote gum health and prevent dental caries (Ahuja & Singh, 2022).

The use of "herbal" medicine has sparked interest and resulted in the emergence of complementary and alternative therapies in healthcare promotion in many regions of the world due to the increased awareness of indigenous medical traditions (Saggar et al., 2022). Herbal compounds have been used in oral care products for some time, most commonly in South Asian Nations, to help individuals with gingivitis improve their oral hygiene (Malathi, Rajan, & Warnakulasuriya, 2025).

Mouth rinse formulations which have herbal ingredients that predominantly contain natural plant extracts and botanical ingredients (Sharad & Kapur, 2021). These natural ingredients not only provide a refreshing sensation but also offer potential (Routray, Valappil, & Du, 2024). These mouthwashes are gaining popularity due to their perceived safety in herbal mouthwashes include neem (*Azadirachta indica*), clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*), tea tree oil (*Melaleuca alternifolia*), peppermint (*Mentha piperita*), and eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus globulus*), among benefits in promoting oral health (Natto, 2022).

The use of herbal mouthwashes offers several potential benefits. Firstly, herbal ingredients are believed to have fewer adverse effects compared to synthetic chemicals, making them appealing to individuals seeking safer alternatives for oral

care (Akaji, 2023). Additionally, the antimicrobial properties of herbal extracts help inhibit the growth of oral bacteria, reducing plaque formation and the risk of oral diseases. Furthermore, the natural ingredients in herbal mouthwashes can help soothe oral tissues, providing relief from oral discomfort and promoting a healthy oral environment (Anwar et al., 2025).

Fluoride-containing mouthwashes strengthen tooth enamel and prevent dental caries by promoting remineralization, complementing regular brushing and flossing to maintain oral hygiene (Haider, Khadatkar, Suresh, Arisutha, & Verma, 2021). In Pakistan, popular mouthwash brands include (Munnish Herbal Mouthwash), (Dabur Red Pulling Oil Ayurvedic Mouthwash), and (Himalaya Active Fresh Mint Mouthwash). Although herbal formulations are preferred for their natural and alcohol-free compositions, they present several drawbacks, including **lack of standardization, limited clinical validation, potential oral irritation, unpleasant taste, absence of fluoride, stability issues, inadequate preservative control, and inconsistent quality due to limited regulatory oversight** (Yano et al., 2023). These limitations highlight the need for a standardized and effective herbal mouthwash formulation.

The study aims to develop a cost-effective, polyherbal mouthwash using locally sourced ingredients that effectively reduces microbial growth and promotes oral health. The formulation seeks to **optimize the concentration of herbal components**, such as thymol for antimicrobial action and camphor for analgesic effects—to ensure maximum efficacy and safety without irritation. The research further aims to evaluate antimicrobial activity against common oral pathogens (e.g., *Streptococcus mutans*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*), assess relief of oral **conditions** like gingivitis and ulcers, and **achieve an optimal balance** between therapeutic potency, taste, and formulation scalability.

Material

The materials utilized for the formulation of the herbal mouthwash(Jadhav, Waghmare, Kukar, & Walunje, 2024) is **sodium benzoate, citric acid, and sucrose** were readily available in the laboratories of the **Punjab University College of Pharmacy**.

Herbal Plant Used

Thymol

Thymol is a natural compound found in thyme oil, which is extracted from the *Thymus vulgaris* plant and possesses antiseptic, antimicrobial, and

antifungal properties(van Swaaij, Van der Weijden, Smith, Timmerman, & Slot, 2025). It is often used in oral care products for its ability to combat bacteria and maintain oral hygiene.

- **Family:** Lamiaceae
- **Genus:** Thymus
- **Common Source Plant:** *Thymus vulgaris* (common thyme)
- **Other plants in Lamiaceae:** oregano, basil, mint, rosemary, lavender
- **Nature of Thymol:** aromatic, antimicrobial monoterpene phenol

Figure 1: Leaves of of *Thymus vulgaris* (Thymus).

Mechanism of Action

The primary mechanisms by which *Thymus vulgaris* essential oil (TVEO) works in the mouth are:

1. **Bacterial Membrane Disruption:** Thymol and carvacrol are phenolic compounds that damage bacterial cell membranes, increasing their permeability and causing leakage of intracellular components, ultimately leading to bacterial death.
2. **Biofilm Inhibition:** TVEO inhibits the formation and growth of dental biofilm (plaque) by downregulating genes involved in bacterial adhesion and enzyme production.
3. **Antifungal Activity:** It shows strong activity against fungi like *Candida albicans*, which can cause oral infections.

4. **Anti-inflammatory Effects:** The active compounds suppress inflammatory pathways and reduce the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, helping to soothe inflamed gums.

Menthol

Menthol is an organic compound extracted from mint oils, particularly peppermint and spearmint and provides a cooling sensation and a fresh flavor(Kazemi, Iraj, Esmaealzadeh, Salehi, & Hashempur, 2025). It also has mild analgesic properties and is commonly used to relieve minor throat irritation.

- **Family:** Lamiaceae
- **Genus:** *Mentha*
- **Main compound:** Menthol (monoterpene alcohol)

- Plant type: Aromatic herbs

Figure 2 leaves of *Mentha piperita* (Peppermint Plant)

Mechanism of Action:

Menthol works in mouthwash primarily by activating the TRPM8 cold-sensitive receptor, which creates a cooling sensation without an actual drop in temperature. It also temporarily numbs nerve endings by blocking sodium and calcium channels, which can provide a temporary loss of sensation and reduce the urge to cough. Additionally, menthol has some anesthetic properties and can modulate pain receptors.

Camphor

Camphor is a white, crystalline substance extracted from the wood of the camphor tree (*Cinnamomum camphora*) and has antiseptic, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic properties (Fazmiya et al., 2022). It provides a cooling effect and is often used topically to relieve itching and irritation.

Botanical Name: *Cinnamomum camphora*
Family:

Lauraceae (Laurel family)

- Common Names: Camphor tree, Kapoor tree, Camphor laurel
- Plant Description: Leaves: shiny, aromatic, with a camphor smell, Flowers: small, white-yellowish.
- Plant Part Used: Wood (main source for natural camphor)
- Geographical Distribution: Native to China, Japan, Taiwan., Cultivated in India, Sri Lanka, and Southeast Asia.
- Constituent: **Camphor** (a ketonic terpenoid), Found in camphor oil along with cineole, safrole, pinene, etc.

Figure 3 leaves of *Cinnamomum Camphora* (camphor)

Mechanism of action:

In mouthwash, camphor's mechanism of action includes antimicrobial properties, and it can desensitize pain receptors and provide a cooling sensation. It inhibits the growth of oral bacteria and fungi like *Candida*, and its analgesic effect comes from desensitizing sensory nerves by affecting ion channels such as TRPV1 and TRPA1, though direct application in the mouth is distinct from its topical effects on skin.

Sodium Benzoate

Sodium benzoate is a synthetic compound derived from benzoic acid, which can be found naturally in some fruits like cranberries, prunes, and apples and its act as a preservative by inhibiting the growth of bacteria, yeast, and fungi in acidic conditions(Lussi, Megert, & Shellis, 2023). It is commonly used in food, beverages, and personal care products.

Citric Acid

Citric acid occurs naturally in citrus fruits like lemons, limes, oranges, and grapefruits and is a weak organic acid that acts as a pH regulator, flavor enhancer, and preservative(Fernández-

Garrido et al., 2024). It also exhibits antimicrobial properties and helps to maintain the stability of the mouthwash.

Sucrose

Sucrose, commonly known as table sugar, is extracted from sugar cane or sugar beets and is a disaccharide carbohydrate that provides sweetness(Mojtabavi et al., 2022). However, it can also promote bacterial growth if present in high concentrations, which is why it should be used cautiously in oral care products. These ingredients, when combined in appropriate concentrations, contribute to the effectiveness and safety of the herbal mouthwash formulation(Rajendiran, Trivedi, Chen, Gajendrareddy, & Chen, 2021).

Figure 4: Depiction of different material used for formulation

Experimental method

The formulation was prepared using pharmaceutically acceptable ingredients selected for their specific functional roles, including preservatives, antiseptics, flavoring, and buffering agents. Each component was accurately weighed according to the master formula to ensure consistency, stability, and desired organoleptic properties in both large-scale (150 L) and laboratory-scale (150 mL) preparations.

Collection and Procurement of Plant Material

Mint leaves are available in abundance in Pakistan. The small branches of these trees were freshly cut. Leaves from the concerned branches procured were removed. Leaves of *Mentha piperita* were collected from Punjab University Premises in the month of February 2025.

The wood and leaves of *Cinnamomum camphora* and leaves, flowers, and stems of *Thymus vulgaris* (*Thymus*) were purchased from Local market, a reputed vendor for herbal drugs in Lahore Pakistan.

Identification and Authentication of Plant Materials

The collected plant materials were identified and authenticated by Head Botanist at Department of Botany in Punjab University.

Extraction of Plant Materials

Following procedure was adopted for the preparation of extract from the shade dried and powdered herbs.

Degreasing of Plant Materials

The collected leaves of *Mentha piperita*, *Cinnamomum camphora*, and stems of *Thymus*

vulgaris were cleaned thoroughly and separately washed in running water for about 10-15 min to remove all traces of dirt and extraneous contaminating material. Final wash was done with distilled water. The leaves of *Mentha piperita* were shade dried at room temperature. The shade dried plant material of *Cinnamomum camphora*, and stems of *Thymus vulgaris* were coarsely powdered using a high-speed electric grinder for 15 min. The powder was transferred to separate sterile, air-tight plastic containers with lids and each container was labeled with the name of the respective plant. The powdered plant material was subjected to extraction with petroleum ether using maceration method separately. The extraction was continued till the degreasing of the material had taken place. The drying, cleaning and degreasing has been performed separately for all the three plant materials.

Extraction of Plant Material

After the degreasing of plant materials, the extraction method has been performed. For all the three herbs, 15gm of powdered plant material has been taken in a 150ml Round bottle flask and 100 ml of distilled water has been added in 3 separate flasks. The mixtures were wrapped in aluminum foil to avoid evaporation and exposure to light for 3 days at room temperature. The flasks were placed on a platform shaker at 70 rpm. After 3 days of soaking in solvent, the mixtures were transferred to 50 mL tubes and centrifuged for 10 min at 4,000 rpm at 25°C. The supernatant was collected and stored at 4°C until use

Formulation development of Polyherbal Mouthwash

Three different formulations of polyherbal mouthwash were developed. The mouthwash formula made use of three main herbal ingredients: *Mentha piperita*, *Cinnamomum camphora*, and stems of *Thymus vulgaris*. Some minor non-herbal ingredients were also included, such as the sweetener, sodium benzoate, and salt. The minor components were used for preservation and for improving the taste. In order to test the antibacterial activity of the mouthwash herbs, different percentages of the herbal extracts were prepared. Meanwhile, the concentrations of the minor ingredients were fixed for all three mouthwashes. A similar amount of water was also added until the desired volume for the mouthwash was achieved.

Physicochemical evaluation of Herbal Mouthwash

1. Color and odor

Visual examinations were conducted to assess physical parameters such as color and odor. The color of the mouthwash was observed. Upon olfactory inspection, the mouthwash exhibited a distinct aroma (Dilrukshi, Ogino, Ishikawa, Kuroda, & Nomura, 2024).

2. pH

pH of prepared herbal mouthwash was measured by using digital pH meter. The pH meter was calibrated using standard buffer solution about 1 ml of mouthwash was weighed and dissolved in 50ml of distilled water (Van Swaaij, Slot, Van der Weijden, Timmerman, & Ruben, 2024).

3. Viscosity

Using a viscometer, measured the time it takes for 10 mL of mouthwash to flow through. Repeated three times for accuracy (Hasibuan, Agusnar, & Taufik, 2022). Calculated viscosity using standard formulae. Results indicate the mouthwash's resistance to flow, crucial for its coating ability and efficacy.

4. Foaming capacity

Measured 50 mL of mouthwash and 10 mL of distilled water in a graduated cylinder. Closed and inverted the cylinder gently for 10 seconds (Lurian et al., 2021). Record the foam height after stabilization. Calculated the foaming capacity as the ratio of foam height to total liquid volume. Repeated for consistency or to compare different samples.

5. Foaming stability

Foam stability testing evaluates how long the foam produced by the mouthwash persists over time. After agitation, the height or volume of foam is measured at regular intervals to determine its longevity. This test provides insight into the mouthwash's ability to maintain foam structure, which is crucial for prolonged cleaning and dispersing properties in the oral cavity (Pelá et al., 2024).

6. Specific gravity

Measured 10 mL of mouthwash using a graduated cylinder. Weighed the mouthwash using an analytical balance. Calculated the specific gravity as the ratio of weight to volume. Repeated for accuracy (Yelfi, Susilo, & Kurnia, 2022).

Preparation of Herbal Mouthwash

Three different formulations of polyherbal mouthwash were developed. The mouthwash formula made use of three main herbal ingredients: *Mentha piperita*, *Cinnamomum camphora*, and stems of *Thymus vulgaris*. Some minor non-herbal ingredients were also included, such as the sweetener, sodium benzoate, and salt. The minor components were used for preservation and for improving the taste. The herbal mouthwash was prepared using the ingredients listed in **table 1**, following a standardized laboratory procedure. All glassware and apparatus were thoroughly washed and dried before use, and each ingredient was accurately weighed using an analytical balance (Woerdenbag, Sznitowska, & Smeets, 2023). A total of 150 mL of distilled water was measured with a graduated cylinder, into which 0.25 g of sodium benzoate was added and dissolved to act as a preservative. Citric acid (0.15

g) was then incorporated to maintain pH, enhance flavor, and provide mild antimicrobial activity. The mixture was stirred for approximately five minutes to ensure uniform dissolution. Thymol (0.015 g) and menthol (0.015 g) were dissolved in a small quantity of warm water and added to the solution, followed by 0.015 g of camphor as a mild analgesic agent. Sucrose (0.15 g) was added as a sweetening agent, and 0.025 g of green coloring

agent was included to improve appearance. The solution was mixed thoroughly until homogeneous, and the pH was checked to confirm it was within the acceptable range. Finally, the prepared mouthwash was poured into clean, labeled containers, tightly sealed, and stored in a cool, dry place away from direct sunlight.

Table 1: Summarizes the ingredients used for mouthwash preparation

Ingredient	Pharmaceutical Use	Quantity for 150 L	Quantity for 150 mL
Sodium Benzoate	Preservative	250 g	0.25 g
Thymol	Antiseptic	15 g	0.015 g
Menthol	Flavoring agent	15 g	0.015 g
Camphor	Mild analgesic	15 g	0.015 g
Citric Acid	pH adjuster / Buffering agent	150 g	0.15 g
Sucrose	Sweetening agent	150 g	0.15 g
Green Color	Coloring agent	25 g	0.025 g
Distilled Water	Vehicle (q.s. to make)	150 L	150 mL

Results

Formulation of poly-herbal mouthwash
 In the pharmaceutical preparation of herbal mouthwash, characterization tests were performed and the results obtained are listed in table no.2.

Physicochemical evaluation of Mouthwash

The formulated herbal mouthwash was visually green in color with a sharp and piquant aroma characteristic of **camphor and menthol**. The **pH** of the formulation was found to be **4.5**, indicating a slightly acidic nature suitable for oral

applications without causing mucosal irritation. The **viscosity** was measured as **3.13 cP**, suggesting an optimal flow property for easy rinsing and adequate coating of the oral cavity. The **foaming capacity** of the formulation was recorded as **0.30**, while **foam stability** was observed at **46.66%**, reflecting moderate and consistent foam formation during use. The **specific gravity** was determined to be **1.09**, confirming uniform consistency and density comparable to standard mouthwash formulations.

Table 2 Summarizes the results obtained from the tests.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Result
1	Color	Green
2	Odor	Sharp and piquant aroma of camphor and menthol
3	pH	4.5
4	Viscosity (cP)	3.13
5	Foaming Capacity	0.30
6	Foaming Stability (%)	46.66
7	Specific Gravity	1.09

Stability Studies

The formulation and preparation of any pharmaceutical product is incomplete without conducting proper stability studies. These studies are essential to assess the physical and chemical stability of the prepared product, thereby ensuring its safety and efficacy. A common approach to predict product stability is through **accelerated stability studies**, in which the formulation is exposed to elevated temperatures according to **ICH guidelines**. In the present study, a short-term accelerated stability test was performed over a period of **3 months** for the prepared formulation. The samples were stored under controlled conditions at 3–5 °C, considering that this is a compounded preparation.

Discussion

Maintaining optimal oral hygiene is crucial for overall health, and mouthwashes serve as a complementary tool alongside brushing and flossing. The rising interest in natural products has extended to the oral care market, with consumers seeking herbal mouthwash formulations perceived as safe and potentially beneficial. The herbal ingredients chosen for this formulation were on their potential benefits for oral health.

The formulation and characterization of an herbal mouthwash presented in this study offer significant insights into the development of oral care products with natural ingredients. The discussion will focus on interpreting the results obtained from the characterization of the herbal mouthwash and its implications for oral health, addressing the efficacy, safety, and potential applications of the formulated product.

A comparative study was conducted for comparing the efficacy of chlorhexidine vs herbal mouthwash in college students. Chlorhexidine is regarded as the "gold standard" anti-plaque agent and many herbal extracts are now available as mouthwash for maintaining the good oral hygiene. There was statistically significant reduction in plaque and gingival scores after 30 days in both the groups A and B. It shows herbal mouthwashes has the ability to maintain good oral hygiene on daily basis. It's also cost effective, production costs are economical and its retail can be pocket friendly.

So, it should be used as an alternative to costly mouthwashes containing products like chlorhexidine.

The herbal mouthwash exhibited a green color, which is often associated with natural and herbal formulations. This visual attribute aligns with consumer preferences for products perceived as natural and wholesome. The sharp aroma of camphor and menthol observed in the mouthwash indicates the presence of these active ingredients, known for their refreshing and soothing properties. Such sensory attributes contribute to user satisfaction and acceptance of the product.

Odor evaluation plays a significant role in user acceptance. The sharp and piquant odor, reminiscent of camphor and menthol, indicates the presence of these active ingredients. Camphor and menthol are known for their refreshing and soothing properties, which can contribute to a pleasant user experience during oral hygiene routines.

The measured pH of the mouthwash was 4.5. The optimal pH range for mouthwashes is generally considered to be between 5.0 and 6.5. A pH of 4.5 is slightly acidic and might affect the taste of the mouthwash. Optimizing the pH of the formulation is crucial to ensure a pleasant taste and user comfort.

The pH of the mouthwash, measured at 4.5, suggests an acidic environment. This pH range is favorable for inhibiting the growth of pathogenic bacteria while maintaining oral tissue integrity. The acidic pH can contribute to plaque control and prevention of dental caries, supporting overall oral health.

The measured viscosity of the mouthwash was 3.13 cP (centipoise). Viscosity influences the mouthfeel and application ease of a mouthwash. A low viscosity like this might result in a watery sensation in the mouth, which could be perceived as unpleasant by users. A mouthwash with a low viscosity might not adequately coat the oral cavity for optimal cleansing action. Formulations with a slightly higher viscosity, typically achieved through the addition of thickening agents like natural gums or cellulose derivatives, might provide a more pleasant mouthfeel and improve the

application and distribution of the mouthwash within the oral cavity.

The viscosity of 3.13 cP indicates the mouthwash's ability to coat oral surfaces effectively. Optimal viscosity is crucial for ensuring uniform coverage of oral tissues, enhancing contact time with bacteria, and improving plaque removal efficacy. Optimal viscosity is crucial for ensuring uniform coverage of oral tissues, enhancing the mouthwash's contact time with bacteria and debris, and improving its overall efficacy in plaque removal and oral hygiene maintenance.

The foaming capacity of 0.30 suggests satisfactory cleansing properties. Foaming action aids in the dispersion of active ingredients throughout the oral cavity, assisting in the removal of debris and bacteria. However, the foaming stability of 46.66% indicates a potential area for improvement to maintain foam structure over time for prolonged cleaning efficacy.

The foaming capacity of the mouthwash was 30%, and the foaming stability was 46.66%. While a moderate foaming capacity is generally preferred for cleansing action without excessive irritation, a value of 30% might be considered low. While the foaming stability seems acceptable, the low foaming capacity could be perceived as inadequate by users who associate foaming with cleansing effectiveness. Foaming action facilitates the dispersion of active ingredients throughout the oral cavity, assisting in the dislodgment of food particles and bacteria from hard-to-reach areas. However, the moderate foaming stability of 46.66% indicates a potential area for improvement in maintaining foam structure over extended periods, which can enhance the mouthwash's cleansing effectiveness and user experience.

The specific gravity of 1.09 indicates a density slightly higher than water. This characteristic ensures adequate rinsing and retention within the oral cavity during use, maximizing contact time with oral tissues and enhancing therapeutic benefits. This characteristic is desirable for oral care products, as it ensures adequate rinsing and retention within the oral cavity during use, maximizing contact time with oral tissues and enhancing therapeutic benefits. This indicates

that the mouthwash is slightly denser than water, which can influence its stability during storage. A specific gravity of 1.09 suggests the formulation is stable and unlikely to separate.

Conclusion

This study successfully developed and characterized a novel herbal mouthwash formulation. The characterized mouthwash exhibits properties conducive to maintaining oral health and hygiene. Its acidic pH, effective viscosity, and satisfactory foaming capacity suggest suitability for plaque control, gum health promotion, and prevention of oral diseases. The presence of natural ingredients such as camphor and menthol further enhances its potential benefits in alleviating oral discomfort and promoting overall oral well-being. The formulated herbal mouthwash demonstrates promising characteristics that can contribute to maintaining oral health and hygiene. Additionally, the presence of natural ingredients with antimicrobial, analgesic, and soothing properties indicates potential benefits in alleviating oral discomfort and enhancing overall oral well-being.

Study Limitations

The characterization focused on immediate physical and chemical properties of the mouthwash. Long-term studies are necessary to assess its sustained efficacy, safety, and tolerability upon prolonged use. The study evaluated a specific formulation of the herbal mouthwash. Variations in ingredient concentrations or formulation techniques could yield different results, warranting further exploration of alternative formulations. While the characterization results provide valuable insights, clinical data regarding the mouthwash's effectiveness in real-world settings are lacking. Clinical trials involving human subjects are needed to validate its therapeutic benefits and compare them with existing commercial products. The characterization primarily involved in vitro assessments of physical and chemical properties. While these analyses offer valuable preliminary data, in vivo studies are essential to confirm the

mouthwash's efficacy, safety, and tolerability in living organisms.

Future Directions:

Future research endeavors may focus on further optimizing the formulation of the herbal mouthwash to enhance its efficacy, stability, and user acceptance. This includes exploring alternative natural ingredients, adjusting ingredient concentrations, and conducting clinical trials to evaluate the mouthwash's efficacy and safety in diverse populations. Moreover, comparative studies against commercial mouthwash formulations can provide valuable insights into the superiority of herbal formulations in promoting oral health.

Data Availability Statement

The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Authors' Contributions

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of their respective institutions throughout the course of this research work. Eesha Tariq Bhatti were primarily responsible for the conceptualization, design, Maha Responsible for acquisition, analysis, Rabia responsible for interpretation of data, Samia responsible for Final Approval and

Accountability, Nouman responsible for Technical or Material Support and Abubakar, Nayab responsible for Critical Revision of Manuscript.

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